

Exploring Pre-service Teachers' Content Knowledge of Grade 11 Euclidean Geometry learnt with GeoGebra

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Abstract

This study examines pre-service teachers' Content Knowledge (CK) in Euclidean geometry. It is premised on the assertion that the effectiveness of teaching and learning in Euclidean geometry is shaped by teachers' conceptual understanding and instructional practices. The TPACK framework guided the investigation of participants' ability to integrate technology into the teaching of Euclidean geometry. Data were collected through questionnaires administered to pre-service teachers. The findings revealed that pre-service teachers exhibited limited knowledge of Euclidean geometry. The study recommends broadening mathematics education research in South Africa to prioritise pre-service teachers' TCK development.

Key words: Pre-service teachers, Euclidean geometry, Content Knowledge (CK), GeoGebra

Introduction

Mathematics is generally acknowledged as the rational language that underlies sciences, technology, engineering, medicine, and the social sciences (Smith, 2004). An effective teaching of mathematics intends to make abstract ideas understandable and enable problem-solving skills to tackle complex problems (Steedly et al., 2008). Geometry is a core branch in mathematics that deals with the properties and relationships of points, lines, angles, and basic geometric figures (Brannan, Esplen and Gray, 2002). It develops spatial thinking and an understanding of the structure of shapes and is generally categorized into branches like plane geometry, solid geometry, spherical geometry, Euclidean geometry, and analytical geometry (Ndinda, 2016; Jin et al., 2021).

In Euclidean geometry, circle theorems are an important aspect that helps learners and mathematicians comprehend circular geometry, orientation, and relationships (Badu-Domfeh 2020). It is one of the most valuable topics in mathematics education and is assessed in Paper 2 in the Grade 12 National Senior Certificate examination. Studying Euclidean geometry

improves learners' critical thinking skills, visualization, problem-solving, conjecturing, and proof, which are important skills for success in the modern world (Mudhefi, 2022). Despite its significance in mathematics, Euclidean geometry is the most difficult parts of geometry, and as a result, learners are performing poorly (Kwadwo and Asomani, 2021). Teaching this topic effectively, therefore, requires educators to use diverse approaches that combine in-depth knowledge of the subject, innovative teaching practices, emotional intelligence, and technology (Patkin and Lavenberg 2012).

The effective teaching of Euclidean geometry is rarely achieved in the South African education system. Instead, it poses challenges to learners in secondary schools, who often find it difficult to understand the concepts and apply the principles (Luneta, 2014; Siyephu and Mtonjeni, 2014). As a result, there has been concerns about persistent poor performance in Euclidean geometry (Bowie 2009; Ngirish and Bansilal 2019; Luneta 2014; Lee and Ginsburg 2009; Siyepu and Mtonjeni 2014). Research in mathematics education in South Africa attributes these challenges to teachers limited pedagogical knowledge (Tachie 2020; Kyabuntu and Mbhiza 2024; Ngirishi and Bansilal 2015). Many teachers struggle with both the content knowledge and pedagogical expertise required to teach the topic effectively (Tachie, 2020). In classrooms, teaching often relies heavily on a question-and-answer approach, which, while encouraging participation, does not sufficiently support learners' conceptual understanding or help them see the interconnections between geometric ideas (Kyabuntu and Mbhiza, 2024).

Consequently, mathematics learners in South Africa continue to experience significant difficulties in learning Euclidean geometry, which negatively affects both their performance and their confidence in the subject. Brijlall and Abakah (2022) reports that learners often lack a deep understanding of Euclidean geometry, which prevents them from making meaningful connections across geometric concepts when solving problems. Similarly, the findings of Ngirishi and Bansilal (2019) reveal that learners struggle with defining geometric terms, understanding the interrelationships among properties and shapes, recognising class inclusion, and interpreting different semiotic representations. Despite Euclidean geometry comprising approximately 50 (± 3) marks in the examination, the Grade 12 National Diagnostic Report of the Department of Basic Education (2024) continues to highlight poor learner performance in this section.

While learners' performance is often a reflection of the depth of their learning and understanding of mathematical concepts, it is equally important to acknowledge that educators'

pedagogical reasoning and classroom practices in Euclidean geometry play a crucial role in promoting knowledge retention and effective preparation for assessment. These practices are largely influenced by the quality of professional training that pre-service mathematics teachers receive to become competent in teaching Euclidean geometry at high school level. Studies concerning pre-service mathematics teachers' knowledge of mathematics exist in South Africa, however, few of them concentrate on pre-service teachers' content knowledge of Euclidean geometry. This remained a notable gap in research concerning pre-service teachers' content knowledge for teaching Euclidean geometry. **With this gap in mind, we formulated the research question for this study:**

What content knowledge do pre-service teachers demonstrate in Grade 11 Euclidean geometry?

Literature Review

Transitioning to democracy in South Africa in 1994 had several curriculum changes which impacted mathematics education, especially the teaching of Euclidean geometry. Mathematics teachers have been facing challenges to effectively teach Euclidean geometry due to a lack of preparation and exposure of the curriculum requirements (Bowie, 2009). As a result, inadequate preparedness with Euclidean geometry content and teaching skills had emerged within mathematics education curriculum (Luthuli, 1996). Currently, the South African education system is underpinned by the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) of which Euclidean geometry is included in Grades 10 to 12 mathematics curriculum (Herbst et al., 2017). Although the inclusion of Euclidean geometry was positively received under CAPS, existing challenges related to teachers' pedagogical knowledge in this domain remained unaddressed (Ndlovu 2013; Govender 2014).

Research studies in mathematics education in South Africa have increasingly emphasized challenges in the teaching and learning of Euclidean geometry. These include teachers' lack of content knowledge and poor teaching practices (Tachie, 2020, Marange and Tatira, 2023; Kyabuntu and Mbhiza, 2024). Some teachers rely solely on a question-and-answer approach to engage learners, without providing sufficient explanations or scaffolding (Kyabuntu and Mbhiza, 2024). Similarly, the teacher-centered approach was observed as dominant in most high schools, where teachers encourage passive learning without engaging learners during the lesson (Marange and Tatira, 2023). Further to this, Tachie (2020) reported that mathematics teachers in South Africa lack both content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge necessary for effective instruction in Euclidean geometry. These insufficient knowledge components

undermine teachers' understanding of geometric concepts, resulting in poor lesson preparation and ineffective teaching. As a result, students taught by these teachers are most likely to underperform in Euclidean geometry topic (Wei et al., 2017). This underperformance by students was revealed by Brijlall (2021) and Ozkan et al. (2018) who asserted that Grade 12 students experience challenges Euclidean geometry due to lack of foundational mathematical skills.

One way of understanding such expertise or lack thereof is through conducting research with teachers, as it is a central premise for mathematic education that teachers play a critical role in ensuring that learners learn and own knowledge and skills for Euclidean geometry. While previous studies attribute challenges related to teachers' knowledge of teaching Euclidean geometry, there is the scarcity of research that explores pre-service teachers' knowledge of Grade 11 Euclidean geometry within the South African context. Considering that pre-service teachers are trained to embark on the journey to become competent qualified teachers, this study sought to explore and understand their content knowledge in Euclidean geometry at Grade 10 level, to address the identified gap.

Theoretical Framework: Understanding Teachers' Content Knowledge of Euclidean geometry with GeoGebra

This study sought to explore the content knowledge of pre-service teachers in Euclidean geometry. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, which extends Shulman's (1986) notion of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) by incorporating technology in teaching and learning, grounded the study. TPACK encompasses seven interrelated knowledge domains, each highlighting specific knowledge and skills that teachers must possess: technological knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), content knowledge (CK), pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), technological content knowledge (TCK), technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK), and technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). Figure 1 below is the diagram illustrating the TPACK model:

Figure 1: Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge [Adapted from Koehler and Mishra (2009), p.63]

The interplay of these constructs of knowledge, as shown in Figure 1, is of primary importance in the TPACK framework, as they show the complete knowledge base needed in the effective teaching with the help of technology (Harris, Mishra, & Koehler, 2009). These interplays show how the integration of technology is possible in the teaching of subjects. The interplay of CK, PK, and TK gives rise to three forms of integrating knowledge: pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), technological content knowledge (TCK), and technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK).

This current research utilized content knowledge (CK), a part of the TPACK model, to examine pre-service teachers' content knowledge of Euclidean geometry learned in a GeoGebra-based setting. The TPACK model is relevant to this research because pre-service teachers in a University of Technology setting are expected to be familiar with technological tools required to learn Euclidean geometry. Technological tools are viewed as a part of technology in teaching (Zhang et al., 2023). The level to which pre-service teachers learn Euclidean geometry might also be influenced by technology in the classroom setting. The content knowledge (CK) part of TPACK is relevant to this research in assessing pre-service teachers' knowledge of Euclidean geometry in various domains.

Methodology

This study used a questionnaire to collect data among pre-service teachers (Ndlovu & Brijlall, 2025). Using this data collection tool, quantitative data was obtained from third-year Bachelor of Education pre-service teachers to investigate their experiences with learning Euclidean

geometry at a secondary school level and again at a university level. Quantitative data were analyzed to obtain objective, first-hand information about pre-service teachers' knowledge in Euclidean geometry. The study's population consisted of fifty registered third-year pre-service teachers. They were invited to participate in this study. In addition, thirty-one pre-service teachers participated voluntarily in this study considering that they had the right to withdraw from this study at any time given time (Creswell, 2007). Prior to developing the questionnaire for this study, the researcher reviewed an existing questionnaire developed for the purpose of conducting research using the TPACK framework (Schmidt et al. 2009). Although this questionnaire successfully captures all aspects of the TPACK framework, it remains general and does not focus on exploring any given topic or subject. Therefore, the researcher developed an original questionnaire specifically designed to focus on this study's research question.

The questionnaire was administered to each participant with the aim of collecting data directly relevant to this research question. Additionally, a pilot study with five third-year Bachelor of Education pre-service mathematics educators, who did not participate in the main study, was conducted to further validate the instrument. The final questionnaire was administered pre-service mathematics educators who were the main participants of the study. This research used purposive sampling since it does not aim to generalise findings to broader population (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007). Pre-service teachers were selected based on their direct experience with the central phenomenon under investigation, namely learning Euclidean geometry.

Data Analysis and Discussion

This study uses descriptive statistical methods were used, including frequency distributions and percentage calculations. These descriptive statistics enabled a systematic representation of participants' perceptions, experiences, and levels of understanding of Euclidean geometry concepts mediated through GeoGebra. Such analyses allow for the identification of patterns and trends in the data, thereby providing a foundational overview of pre-service teachers' experiences with Euclidean geometry. The quantitative data in this study not only offered insight into the current experiences of pre-service teachers but also provided a basis for the subsequent qualitative phase, which seeks to explore more deeply the nature and sources of

these perceptions. The descriptive demographic data presented in this section comprises the profile of the pre-service educators, specifically focusing on gender, age group, and year of Grade 12 completion. Although these demographic variables do not form part of the main research aims, they are essential for providing contextual background about the participants and the environment in which the study was conducted. Such information offers insight into the diversity and representativeness of the pre-service teachers, which is relevant when considering issues related to access, equity, and inclusion in mathematics education.

For example, age differences among participants may reveal variations in their experiences of learning Euclidean geometry or differences in their attitudes towards teaching it. Similarly, data on the year of Grade 12 completion provide insight into participants' exposure to different curriculum reforms during their schooling. Notably, learners who completed schooling between 2008 and 2009 did not study Euclidean geometry because it had been removed from the National Curriculum Statement (NCS) during that period. Additionally, the gender distribution of the sample offers useful information about gender dynamics within mathematics education.

The demographic factors can interact in subtle yet meaningful ways with the reported findings, influencing participants' perceptions, beliefs, and experiences. Considering these factors not only enhances the descriptive richness of the sample but also enables the identification of potential demographic patterns that may be relevant for future research. A summary of the age distribution of the pre-service teachers who completed the questionnaire is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Age differences of pre-service mathematics teachers

Age range	Frequency	Percentage
20 – 22	18	58.06
23 – 25	7	22.58
26 – 29	2	6.45
30 +	4	12.90
Total	31	100

Figure 2: A pie chart showing pre-service teachers' age difference

The pie chart in Figure 2 shows that pre-service teachers aged 20–22 years constitute the largest proportion of participants, accounting for 58.06%. This is followed by those aged 23–25 years, and then participants aged 30 years and above. The smallest group, representing 6.45%, consists of pre-service educators aged 26–29 years. Although age is not directly used to answer the research questions in this study, it was included to determine whether variations in pre-service teachers' experiences with Euclidean geometry might be associated with age differences. The distribution of questionnaires was therefore not influenced by any form of bias but rather reflects the actual demographic composition of the sampled population. The gender distribution of the participants is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Gender distribution of pre-service teachers

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	24	77.42
Female	7	22.58
Total	31	100

In Table 2, 77.42% of the pre-service teachers are male, while 22.58% are female. This reflects an unequal gender distribution, with substantially more male than female participants in the study. Such an imbalance points to a broader gender gap within the mathematics education programme at the University of Technology, where male student enrolment appears to exceed that of females. These findings align with Rubel and Shahbari (2024), who note the persistent underrepresentation of female educators in mathematics education.

The gender variation observed in this study may be influenced by a range of socio-cultural, institutional, and historical factors that shape enrolment patterns and career aspirations in mathematics. This has implications for the future diversity of mathematics educators and potentially affects how mathematics education and mathematics more broadly, is experienced and understood by future learners (Rubel and Shahbari 2024).

The years in which the participating pre-service teachers completed Grade 12 were also considered an important demographic factor in this chapter. This provides insight into their academic trajectories and the variations in learning opportunities or experiences they may have had. For example, pre-service teachers who completed Grade 12 in 2008 may have different levels of understanding of Euclidean geometry compared to those who completed secondary schooling more recently. These differences are important for interpreting variation and academic preparedness across the sample. Table 3 below presents the distribution of pre-service teachers by the year in which they completed Grade 12, offering a clearer picture of the cohort's educational history and potential generational differences in exposure to mathematics education.

Table 3: The distribution of pre-service teachers' year of Grade 12 completion

Year of Grade 12 completion	Frequency	Percentage
2008 – 2013	5	16,13
2014 – 2017	12	38,71
2018 – 2021	14	45,16
Total	31	100

From Table 3, 14 (45.16%) pre-service teachers completed Grade 12 between 2018 and 2021, 12 (38.7%) completed between 2014 and 2017, and 5 (16.13%) completed between 2008 and 2013. This indicates an unequal distribution in the years of Grade 12 completion, which has implications for their experiences with Euclidean geometry. Notably, between 2008 and 2013, Euclidean geometry was removed from the compulsory mathematics curriculum. Consequently, pre-service teachers who completed school during this period may have had limited or no formal exposure to Euclidean geometry, unlike those who completed between 2014 and 2021, when the topic had been reinstated in the curriculum.

These differences suggest variability in the depth of Euclidean geometry knowledge acquired at secondary school level. Such variation is likely to influence how well-prepared pre-service teachers feel to engage with, understand, and ultimately teach Euclidean geometry effectively. Overall, the findings highlight that participating pre-service teachers' prior exposure to Euclidean geometry is not uniform and may impact their readiness to work with geometry content in a GeoGebra-mediated context.

Pre-service educators' experiences learning Euclidean Geometry

Table 4 provides a summary of pre-service teachers' experiences with learning Euclidean geometry, both during their secondary schooling and at university level. This information offers valuable insight into their prior exposure to the topic and the extent to which learning in this mathematical domain has been continuous or fragmented across different educational phases.

Table 4: Pre-service teachers' response to their experiences of learning Euclidean geometry at a secondary school and university level

QUESTIONS	OPTIONS	
	Yes	No
1. Did you learn Euclidean geometry in high school	22	9
2. If yes, how did you find it?	Easy	Difficult
	8	14
3. Did you learn Euclidean geometry at the university?	Yes	No
	31	0
4. If yes, how did you find it?	Yes	No
	18	13

Table 4 summarises the responses of pre-service teachers regarding their experiences of learning Euclidean Geometry at both secondary and university levels. The questionnaire was completed by 31 pre-service teachers. Question One shows that 22 (70.96%) pre-service teachers studied Euclidean Geometry during their secondary school education, whereas 9 (29.03%) did not. This indicates that most participants in this study had prior exposure to Euclidean Geometry, while a smaller proportion did not. Among those who studied Euclidean Geometry, 14 (63.63%) reported that they found it difficult to learn at secondary school. This suggests that completing Grade 12 within the revised CAPS curriculum does not necessarily guarantee strong content knowledge in Euclidean Geometry. These findings are supported by Brijlall (2022) and Modhefi (2022), who reported that Grade 12 learners often experience difficulties in Euclidean Geometry, hindering their ability to make connections across

geometry concepts to solve problems. The insufficient instruction at the secondary school level may contribute to these challenges (Ogbonnaya and Bogoshi 2024; Mukuka and Alex 2024). The study also revealed that pre-service teachers' experiences with Euclidean Geometry at university differ from their experiences at secondary school. The results from Question 3 showed that all thirty-one participating pre-service teachers learned Euclidean Geometry in their mathematics module at the university level. Of these, 27 (90%) reported that they found Euclidean Geometry easy to learn, while 4 (10%) indicated difficulty. This difference may be attributed to more effective teaching and learning practices at university compared to secondary school. Previous studies have also shown that pre-service teachers exhibit greater confidence and stronger conceptual understanding of geometry when instruction is supported by technology and learner-centred approaches at tertiary institutions (Mokotjo and Mokhele-Makgalwa 2021; Machisi 2021). In addition, the integration of visual and interactive tools such as GeoGebra has been shown to improve understanding of geometrical concepts by making abstract ideas more concrete and accessible (Amir and Sari 2018). Enhanced instructional design and professional support at university, compared to secondary school, may further contribute to higher levels of comprehension and more positive attitudes toward geometry among pre-service teachers (Ngirishi and Bansilal 2019; Kivkovich and Chis 2016).

Pre-service mathematics educators' content knowledge (CK) of Euclidean Geometry

In Question 5, the aim was to evaluate whether pre-service teachers possess content knowledge in Euclidean Geometry. This item was designed to determine their understanding of Euclidean Geometry, including theorems and properties of other geometric concepts. An assessment rubric was used to score participants' performance, and the scores were subsequently classified into three categories, as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Pre-service teachers' performance in a Euclidean geometry question

Marks	Percentage	Category	Pre-service teachers' performance
0 – 3	0% - 30%	Poor	Showing a fundamental misunderstanding or significant error.
4 – 5	40% - 50%	Average	Showing an incomplete understanding validated by some errors or partial application of concepts.
6 – 7	60% - 99%	Good	Showing good complete understanding with minor errors.
10	100%	Outstanding	Showing a complete understanding with no errors found.

Figure 5 shows the format of Question 5, which is used as an instrument to gauge the understanding of pre-service teachers in this topic.

QUESTION 5

In the diagram below, PWRS is a cyclic quadrilateral in the circle, centered at O. $\triangle PSW$ is an equilateral triangle. TW is a tangent to the circle at W. Radii OR and OW are drawn. Angle $W_5 = 25^\circ$

Determine, with reasons, the size of angle R_1

Figure 3: Question 5 of the questionnaire

All thirty-one pre-service teachers responded to this question item and their scores are summarised in Table 6 and a bar graph in Figure 4.

Table 6.6: Pre-service mathematics educators' scores in Question 5

Year of Gr.12 completion	Rubric score $\left(\frac{\text{score}}{10}\right)$					
	QUESTION 5					
	Incorrect		partially correct		correct	
	students	(%)	students	(%)	Students	(%)
2008 – 2013	3	6.81	2	4,55	0	0
2014 – 2017	8	18.18	4	9,09	0	0
2018 – 2021	22	50.00	3	6,82	2	4.55
Total	31	74,99	9	20,46	2	4.55

Figure 4: Pre-service teachers' performance in Question 5 in the questionnaire

The statistical data presented above reveals a concerning trend in pre-service teachers' knowledge of secondary-school Euclidean geometry. Among those who completed Grade 12 between 2008 and 2013, only 6.81% performed poorly in this question. However, the proportion of incorrect responses increased to 18.18% for those who completed Grade 12 between 2014 and 2017 and rose even more sharply by 50%, among those who completed Grade 12 between 2018 and 2021. Overall, 75.36% of the pre-service teachers provided incorrect answers to Question 5, indicating a significant deficit in their Euclidean geometry content knowledge. These results demonstrate that future mathematics teachers, regardless of their Grade 12 completion year, tend to possess a weak understanding of Euclidean geometry. Such gaps in content knowledge raise concerns about their readiness to teach geometry effectively. These statistical findings are consistent with Mukuka and Alex (2024), who highlight that mathematics teachers often exhibit low proficiency in school-level geometry, reflecting weaknesses in teacher training programmes. The results also align with Tachie (2020), who noted that many educators lack both content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge for teaching geometry effectively, while learners continue to struggle with circle theorems, resulting in poor performance (Kwadwo and Asomani 2021). In this study, only a small proportion of pre-service teachers (3.07%) demonstrated a high level of proficiency in Euclidean geometry. However, even this level of mastery does not automatically translate into effective teaching, as content knowledge alone does not guarantee pedagogical competence.

Pre-service mathematics teachers' knowledge of integrating dynamic software in Euclidean geometry

Teaching Euclidean Geometry involves a range of challenges, including pedagogical and methodological difficulties, as well as the insufficient integration of technology. Maqoqa (2024) emphasizes that these factors can substantially impede both teaching and learning in the context of Euclidean Geometry. Table 7 shows pre-service mathematics teachers' knowledge of integrating dynamic software in Euclidean Geometry.

Table 7: Distribution of dynamic mathematics software that pre-service teachers can use to teach Euclidean geometry

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
A – Geometer's Sketchpad	0	0
B – Autograph	0	0
C – GeoGebra	3	9,67%
D – None	28	90,32%

In Table 7, 90.32% of pre-service teachers indicated that they are not proficient in using any of the listed dynamic mathematics software, including GeoGebra. This suggests that pre-service teachers in this study lack not only Euclidean geometry content knowledge but also the ability to integrate dynamic mathematics software as an effective technological tool for teaching Euclidean geometry. This finding aligns with de Freitas and Spangenberg (2019), who reported that mathematics educators often demonstrate insufficient levels of technological knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, and technological content knowledge. Such deficiencies point to inadequate exposure or training in the effective use of technological tools during teacher preparation programmes. As a result, these knowledge gaps may hinder pre-service teachers' ability to meaningfully incorporate dynamic mathematics software into their instructional practice, thereby limiting opportunities to enhance the teaching and learning of Euclidean geometry.

Pre-service mathematics teachers' training on integrating GeoGebra software in mathematics

The responses to Questions 7 to Question 10 of the questionnaire addressed whether pre-service mathematics teachers had received professional training in integrating GeoGebra into their mathematics education curriculum. The results of these questions are presented in Table 8.

Table 6.8 Pre-service mathematics educators' professional development in integrating GeoGebra

Questions		Yes	No
Q7	Have you been equipped with GeoGebra software in teaching Euclidean Geometry?	31	0
Q8	If your answer to Question 7 is yes, mention the topic in Mathematics Module where you were equipped with GeoGebra	Analytical Geometry	Euclidean Geometry
		31	31
Q9	Can you use GeoGebra-specific applications to construct Euclidean Geometry diagrams?	0	31
Q10	Can you prove Euclidean Geometry theorems on a computer using GeoGebra?	0	31

The results in Table 8 reveal a notable discrepancy in the preparedness of pre-service teachers to use GeoGebra for teaching geometry. While all participating pre-service teachers reported having received training on the use of GeoGebra particularly for teaching Analytical Geometry, they did not have opportunities to practise using the software. Consequently, they demonstrated limited ability to use GeoGebra effectively to construct Euclidean geometry diagrams or prove geometric theorems. This suggests that the participants did not acquire the practical skills necessary to integrate GeoGebra into their pedagogical practices.

These findings align with Berhe et al. (2025), who argue that:

Mathematics teachers face challenges in using GeoGebra in their teaching practices due to students' experience with the software, lack of access and support in using technology, university mathematics educators' perceptions, beliefs, and skills in using GeoGebra, lack of funding, adequate infrastructures, training, exposure, and awareness of mathematical software, inadequate staff support, the mathematics curriculum itself, and their resistance to change (Berhe et al. 2025).

This perspective underscores the need for more robust and hands-on training that extends beyond introducing GeoGebra at a theoretical level. Pre-service teachers require practical opportunities to apply GeoGebra in specific mathematical contexts, such as Euclidean Geometry, where the software has strong potential to enhance conceptual understanding. The findings in this study highlight possible gaps in the Mathematics Education curriculum, where emphasis on theoretical knowledge of digital tools may overshadow the development of practical, classroom-oriented application skills.

These results also informed the researcher's decision to conduct a workshop on integrating GeoGebra in geometry teaching with pre-service teachers. This workshop was motivated by the recognition that pre-service teachers are future teachers in the 21st century, and their capacity to integrate technology meaningfully into their teaching will shape learners' classroom experiences. The workshop aimed to strengthen their ability to integrate GeoGebra through professional development activities, consistent with the recommendations of Petras, Jamil and Mohamed (2012).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study demonstrated how pre-service teachers displayed their level of Grade 11 Euclidean geometry learnt' in a GeoGebra-based environment. The results revealed that pre-service teachers, irrespective of the year they completed Grade 12, generally demonstrated lack of

conceptual and procedural understanding of Euclidean Geometry. Furthermore, the study identified a significant gap in pre-service teachers' ability to integrate dynamic mathematical software, specifically GeoGebra, into the learning and teaching of Euclidean Geometry. Overall, lack of understanding Euclidean geometry in pre-service teachers limited opportunities for understanding Euclidean geometry in a GeoGebra-based environment.

We have realised that teaching training pre-service teachers on teaching Euclidean geometry in a technology-driven South African education system, require them to possess content and knowledge about technological tools for teaching the topic effectively.

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